

Role of Media on political socialization of Graduate students in west Tripura District

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Abstract:

The media has been perceived as a powerful agent of political socialization, influencing the political attitudes and behaviour of voters and non-voters alike. The survey commissioned a study on university students in West Tripura district to investigate the effects of print, television and online news on the political socialization of university student. In addition it seeks to explain the role of the media as an effective agent of political socialization of university students. West Tripura District. The results indicate that newspaper and television news use significantly predicted internal political effectiveness and the purpose of participating in politics. Media 'nationality', the motivation to apply for permanent residence, and the period of stay in the United States were explored for possible moderation of media influence in political socialization. The results are discussed within the framework of media influence in political socialization in West Tripura's. In addition it seeks to explain the role of the media as an effective agent of political socialization of university students of West Tripura District. The results indicate that newspaper and television news use significantly predicted internal political effectiveness and the purpose of participating in politics. The results are discussed within the framework of media influence in political socialization in West Tripura.

Introduction:

Political socialization is a decorating process through which people learn about basic political concepts, Behaviour, customs and political policy. People embezzle this information and through a complex process over time these become part of their practical life. Political socialization perpetuates the existing political structure and helps it to function effectively. The functioning of the political system was based on social patterns, powers, opinions, behaviour, habits, behaviour and political information of individuals in a society. Political socialization is influenced by different actors, from families and institutions to the media Agent of political socialization.

No one can deny the pioneering role of the media in empowering the masses Mediate by establishing a link between individuals and authorities in the state. Usually, Young people in almost every society have skills and knowledge about different computer programs and videos Games and the Internet in today's world.

Students from different educational institutions often use modern technology and media through different platforms like e- newspaper , Face book, Instagram, twitter, any other media knowingly or unknowingly they becomes familiar with different perspective especially in politics or political participation.

Objective:

1. The main objective of this paper to find out the role of social media on political socialization of UG & PG students.

2. To know the role of mass media on political socialization of UG & PG students.

Research Question:

3. What roles do the social media play on of political socialization among the Graduate and Post Graduate
4. Been taken from Tripura University and MBB College students in West Tripura District?
5. What roles do the mass media play on of political socialization among the Graduate and Post Graduate students in West Tripura District?

Methodology:

Data was collected through a structured questionnaire coupled with personal interview with the respondents. The data was classified and tabulated taking cognitive, affective and evaluative orientations as dependent variables. 60 samples have. Media and Political Socialization of Students of West Tripura: Media is considered an agent of socialization and as such, it can aid in the development of peoples' attitudes, behaviours and gender expectations. In recent decades internet has opened up technologically mediated environments that have reconfigured the 'political'. It played a crucial role in shaping voters interest and attitudes about an election, politicians and governance of the state. The following table will show the interest and source of information of political measure of the students of west Tripura District.

Table:1 Source of Information

Media	Mostly prefer to get Information	Percentage
Television	06	10 %
Radio	04	6.7 %
Newspaper	15	25.0 %
Internet	11	18.3 %
Face book	13	21.7 %
You tube	11	18.3 %
Total	60	100%

Mass Media & Political Socialization of the students of West Tripura District:

In the present day of modern technology the mass media, particularly social media, plays a crucial role in the life of the individual and the society at large. Mass media and social media provide knowledge, information, and entertainment and also educate the masses. The impact of mass media in our daily lives is so strong that it is even impossible to ignore it. Its

implication on the students of West Tripura District is so powerful compare to others parts of Tripura state, that many students are addicted to the mass media including the social media and cannot live without it even for a few hours because almost everybody has a smart phone access. The responded has been asked few questions based on Media to get the knowledge about the influence of media on them for political orientation.

Table-2

Q.1. Do you have accessed to social media?	Yes	98.25%
	No	1.75%
Q.2. Which social media do you use the most?	Face Book	28.0%
	You Tube	22.0%
	Whatsapp	38.0%
	Google, Twitter	12.0%
Q.3. Why do you use social media?	For news and information	52.3 %
	To interact with friends and family	43.7
	Professional purposes	4.0%

From the above table it is analysis that almost all the students (98.25% of the respondents) have access to social media application like Face book, Whatsapp etc. 12.0% People use social media for different purpose and exactly half of the respondents (52.3%) use social media to collect news and information about the political system and the society. On the other hand nearly half of the respondents (43.7%) exercise these social media outlets to interact with

the society, friends and families. Whereas a small number of the respondents (4%) utilize the social media application for professional purposes. In other words, many students from West Tripura use the social media to collect news and information about the state, government and society. These students collected this news from different sources and various social media applications. Maximum number of the respondents (38.0%) assumes that

their main source of information is Whatsapp, whereas some respondents (12.0%) think that other social media outlets like google and twitter are their main sources of knowledge. On the other hand some respondents (28.0%) think that their main source of information is Face book, while there are a small number of students (22.0% of the respondents) who use YouTube as their main source of information.

Conclusion:

From, the above analysis, it can draw a conclusion that mass media is the main source of information for the higher education students of west Tripura District, particularly the students of Tripura University and other degree and professional colleges. Mass media is a significant source of learning for these students. The role of other agents of political socialization is likely to be surpassed and outshined by mass media. However it is important to mention that these social media also application has a negative impact such as lack of privacy, vulnerability to crime, cyber bullying, misinformation, waste of time and money and many more. The other agents of political socialization like family, political parties, Peer Group any many more are directly and indirectly use media to influence students towards political interest.

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